

1 **How important is replication for lithic analysis?**

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10 **Conflict of Interest**

11 The author declares no conflict of interest.

12

13 **Data availability**

14 Not applicable.

15

16 **Acknowledgements**

17 STH received funding through the interdisciplinary research hub HESCOR (Human & Earth
18 System Coupled Research) at the University of Cologne, supported by the ‘Profilbildung
19 2022’ initiative of the Ministry of Culture and Science of the State of North Rhine-Westphalia
20 (ID: HESCOR PB22-081), and the VolkswagenFoundation’s ‘Pioneering Research –
21 Exploring the Unknown Unknown’ funding line (AZ: 9D767).

22 **Short abstract**

23 *Replication is thought to be a fundamental requirement of securing scientific knowledge. Yet*
24 *replication is not always straightforward, sometimes difficult, and it might even fail—a*
25 *problem now routinely canvassed as the ‘replication crisis’. Lithic researchers have recently*
26 *heeded new attention to the problems and opportunities of testing and improving replicability.*
27 *The author reviews the state of this debate and associated efforts to reform lithic studies,*
28 *showing that it may be premature to declare a replication crisis in the field and that evidence-*
29 *based and epistemologically informed approaches are urgently needed to assess the status*
30 *and importance of replication in lithic analysis.*

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32 **Keywords:** Stone artefacts; metaarchaeology; epistemology; replication crisis; new localism;
33 evidence-based science; good scientific practice

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44 Introduction

45 A new spectre is haunting lithic studies: the so-called ‘replication crisis’ (cf. Ioannidis, 2005;
46 Baker, 2016; Nosek *et al.*, 2022), issued with a firm and persuasive mandate to overhaul
47 traditional research practices and to incite social, methodological, and normative reform
48 (Marwick *et al.*, 2017; Farahani, 2024; Marwick, 2025). A number of widely noticed, high-
49 profile papers in deep-time lithic studies have recently affirmed this crisis (e.g., Pargeter *et*
50 *al.*, 2023; Riede *et al.*, 2024; Kot *et al.*, 2025), pushing concerns of reproducibility and
51 replicability to the centre of the field’s attention. In a similar manner as the majority of other
52 voices who have focalized the alleged replication crisis across the sciences, this nascent
53 debate in archaeology construes the crisis as a universal problem for the credibility of science
54 as a whole and therefore sees little reason to treat lithic studies differently to other fields of
55 inquiry (see esp. Will *et al.*, 2019; Pargeter *et al.*, 2023). Yet, at the same time, metascientists
56 and philosophers of science have pointed out that the empirical claims of the replication crisis
57 as construed – namely that there is such a crisis affecting almost all the sciences in the first
58 place – *may themselves be difficult to replicate*, and the crisis often appears to be fed
59 primarily by aspirational, intuitive, and normative assessments rather than robust empirical
60 evidence (Guttinger, 2020; Pethick, Wass and Michaelis, 2025).

61 The best data suggesting there is indeed a serious replication crisis comes from
62 psychology, where the crisis is controversially debated since the 2010s, and biomedical
63 research (cf. Romero, 2019; Guttinger, 2020; Nosek *et al.*, 2022 for summaries), yet it is
64 often unclear to what precisely such a crisis pertains to, what its scope and actual extent is,
65 and, perhaps most importantly, what degree of replicability we should *expect* in science. A
66 key problem here concerns not just varying technical means and the feasibility of replication
67 across disparate fields of inquiry, but also that different objects of study and target
68 phenomena may in fact be differently amendable to such attempts. In the life sciences, for

69 example, living organisms – even cells, DNA, and proteins – have been shown to often
70 change their responsiveness over time (due to memory, adaptation, etc.), precluding what has
71 been termed direct replication, challenging assumptions about the relationship between
72 replication, precision, and accuracy; they also show that the ability of practitioners to
73 replicate observations and findings may not merely be a function of whether or not (and how
74 closely) they adhere to scientific protocol and rigor, but at least in part also registers the
75 inherent variability of their study objects (Guttinger, 2020). All of this makes it critically
76 important to clarify *what* one aims to replicate, *why* this matters, and what our *expectations*
77 can reasonably be about the outcomes. We often simply do not know the baseline against
78 which we can compare replication outcomes and, to make things worse, baselines may
79 actually vary, not just in relation to different objects of study but also with regard to different
80 *epistemological situations*. To address this requires much more foundational work, I suggest,
81 on the nature and epistemology of lithic analysis than currently undertaken.

82 Scientists often disagree, for example, whether 60% or 80% replication success are
83 evidence for or against a replication crisis – not to speak of unresolved issues of how to
84 measure such success adequately – and the grounding assumption often seems to be that the
85 goal must naturally be to achieve 100% (which is likely impossible). The often cited *Nature*
86 report by Baker (2016), for example, presents evidence only of the *perceptions* of scientists
87 about the reproducibility crisis (it is a survey), and these are often themselves subjective,
88 reflecting relevant opinions, agendas, and epistemic positionalities of those involved. It
89 therefore remains an open question, as Pethick and colleagues (2025: 9f.) remind us, whether
90 the reproducibility crisis really exists, and especially how serious it is in relation to different
91 fields of inquiry, whether it ‘goes significantly beyond inherent experimental variation’, what
92 its size is, and whether it is anchored in research realities or instead turns out to be a
93 ‘consequence of expectations that are based on intuition rather than data’.

94 The present intervention has several aims. The basis of the increasingly invoked
95 replication crisis in lithic studies needs to be openly discussed in print. I want to encourage
96 more caution, critical reflexivity, and epistemological baseline work on the problem, and to
97 urge lithic practitioners to carefully think about the importance of replication in the field
98 (which is far from obvious in my view). Impelled by the ‘new localism’ in the philosophy of
99 replication (Guttinger, 2020), I want to promote a new archaeological metascience examining
100 the reality and extent of the replication crisis in lithic studies as well as serious conversations
101 on the nature of lithic data and the broader knowledge goals of the field.

102

103 **Causes of the replication crisis: do they apply to lithic studies?**

104 Renewing conversations on replication in lithic studies may benefit from critical engagement
105 with the causes of the replication crisis commonly cited. The primary cause of the crisis is
106 generally found to be a particular type of *publication bias*, namely the tendency to rely on the
107 *outcome* of a study (novel findings, hypothesis support, etc.) as the sole criterion for
108 publication (Romero, 2019), in turn framing future research and discourse, and so forth. In
109 fields such as psychology, where the crisis has been most influentially debated, this has often
110 resulted in the need to present statistically significant findings, promoting problematic
111 practices such as ‘p-hacking’ and post-hoc data filtering (Romero, 2019; Nosek *et al.*, 2022),
112 and what Rosenthal (1979) has called the ‘file-drawer problem’. The file-drawer problem
113 points out that under such circumstances, the majority of results (between 95% and 99.5% of
114 true negatives, depending on the set benchmark for statistical significance) will never be
115 published, filling up the file drawers of individual researchers and labs.

116 I would argue that in lithic studies these causes of the crisis do largely not apply. This
117 is because lithic studies remains, for the most part at least, a discovery-driven science, where

118 the yardstick for novelty has traditionally been relatively low as the majority of studies
119 conducted on the lithic material tend to be *first descriptions* of this material. Publication bias
120 primarily applies to where and how different studies are published but this is a different
121 debate. And even if lithic evidence is re-assessed or redescribed, the questions, theories and
122 approaches drawn upon tend to greatly differ. Statistical significance also plays a much less
123 pronounced role as in fields such as psychology, and traditional research practices have
124 primarily relied on descriptive statistics (notably one of the solutions to the replication crisis
125 often cited in the literature). The file-drawer problem of lithic studies appears to be
126 differently configured, too: it applies to lithic objects and assemblages, not so much to
127 negative results; to the contrary, lithic evidence potentially hidden in the drawers (e.g. those
128 of silverback excavators) is typically understood as withdrawn unknowns (novelty) with the
129 potential to transform *positive knowledge*. It often creates an explicit *incentive* for subsequent
130 generations to publish, rather than biasing against certain evidence.

131 Two other causes of the crisis commonly cited – the proliferation of conceptual
132 replication exacerbating publication bias and the problems or misunderstandings of null
133 hypothesis testing (Romero, 2019) – also seem hardly generalizable across the field and
134 arguably find very limited application. This is because they rely on an *empirical claim* that
135 the field commonly operates in a hypothesis-testing mode, with epistemic imports at times
136 converging with the kind of ‘scientific’ archaeology aspired by processualists. This includes
137 the idea that there is a binary space of knowledge: either claims can be reproduced in some
138 relevant ways, or they cannot and must thus be discarded. Not only is it questionable, as
139 pointed out by Penders et al. (2019) with reference to the humanities, whether it should be a
140 goal of lithic research to nail down such a space in the first place, historically and empirically
141 the field has above all been concerned with *enriching* our understanding of the lithic record,
142 resulting in multiple co-existing insights with often-unresolved contiguity. It is at least

143 interesting to note that those pushing for replicability are also those emphatically buying into
144 a specific vision of science the field should aspire to, but such visions are rarely calibrated by
145 an analysis of actual lithic research practices (but see Marwick, 2025).

146 Only the final cause of the replication crisis, namely its rooting in the current reward
147 system of science, its publication structures, and associated within-community values
148 (priority rule, non-incentivizing of replication, etc.) seem to unambiguously apply to lithic
149 studies as well. Importantly, however, these factors mainly contribute to the circumstance that
150 replication is currently not necessarily a priority of lithic research, they do not tell us whether
151 we have reason to believe there is indeed a replication crisis in the field.

152

153 **Towards an archaeological metascience of lithic replication**

154 Declarations of the replication crisis and its relationship with lithic studies are predominantly
155 aspirational and they strongly rely on epistemic intuitions (themselves based on particular,
156 debatable notions of what science ought to be) as well as anecdotal evidence. What is more,
157 the few recently published studies testing the replicability of different lithic observations and
158 results (e.g., Timbrell *et al.*, 2022; Pargeter *et al.*, 2023; Riede *et al.*, 2024; Kot *et al.*, 2025),
159 together with relevant previous work (see e.g. Prentiss, 1998 on lithic débitage typology),
160 have yielded ambivalent or mixed results, and they can be interpreted as showing that many
161 lithic observations and results can actually reasonably be replicated. Pargeter *et al.* (2023), for
162 example, concluded that ‘the most salient finding’ of their study was that ‘international lithic
163 expert analysts performed well across many of the [lithic] attributes tested’. Kot *et al.* (2025),
164 deploying an experimental setup to evaluate lithic scar-biography analysis, similarly
165 concluded that the ‘results obtained indicate the relatively high reliability of the method both
166 from the perspective of intraobserver repeatability and interobserver reproducibility’, while

167 also showing that error rates can be reduced through expertise. In general, most of the studies
168 concerned with lithic replication have concentrated on the replicability of observations rather
169 than previously reported results. While the paucity of such work makes it extremely difficult
170 to assess the reality, scope, and extent of an alleged replication crisis in the field, the evidence
171 that is available does currently not strongly speak in its favour.

172 Given the stakes of the crisis talk – ranging from changing the culture of science to
173 enacting top-down policy measures (Leonelli, 2023; cf. Marwick, 2025) – it would thus be
174 important to take stock of the replication crisis in the same way as other scientific questions
175 are addressed, including *empirically* testing its weight. Only then, I argue, can practitioners
176 reasonably discuss the importance and meaning of replication in lithic analysis. What is
177 called for is therefore not hasty science policies but an *archaeological metascience* of
178 replication, qualitatively and quantitatively investigating scientific processes of lithic analysis
179 to produce evidence that supports or dismisses a replication crisis in the field. In its service, it
180 would be beneficial to invest more resources into precisely those areas of the replication
181 landscape which are currently underdeveloped and to redirect attention to an original core
182 area of concern, namely the *results* of lithic studies. An important part of this could be to
183 promote work on *conceptual replication*, i.e., to test previously published knowledge claims
184 based on different sets of data, methods and/or protocols. It would, however, also need to
185 involve acute attention to the pronounced epistemological diversity of the field (see e.g., de
186 Torre and Mora, 2009; Tostevin, 2011; Perlès, 2016; Hussain, 2019) as different ways of
187 doing lithic research may call for different standards of replication, replication may be
188 varyingly important, and it may point to different issues. What is accordingly required, I
189 suggest, is an informed self-assessment of the field, taking potential localisms more seriously
190 and critically interrogating universalist claims in an evidence-based manner.

191

192 **Lithic data and the goals of the field**

193 The importance of replication in lithic studies is not given, nor is it self-evident. While the
194 expectation that what we consider lithic knowledge should withstand critical scrutiny and
195 repeated revisiting of the grounding evidence may appear unassailable, what this actually
196 means for lithic studies and its broad portfolio of diverse knowledge-making projects with
197 their specific research interests and goals is much less clear. Part of the larger problem, I
198 suggest, has to do with the undertheorized nature of lithic objects and the phenomena
199 typically studied as well as a lack of discussion on *what* should be replicated, and *how*, in a
200 strongly discovery-driven field such as lithic studies.

201 For example, lithic practitioners only ostensibly study inanimate objects or dead
202 matter, in reality they study the behaviours of past lithic technology-yielders producing a
203 patterned lithic record. For this reason alone, and in a similar way as with living organisms
204 (cf. Guttinger, 2020), we cannot expect cases of empirical replication to consist in close-to-
205 perfect data-matching. This is true for different approaches to the lithic record. If we are for
206 instance interested in past ways of exploiting different lithic raw materials, we cannot expect
207 that the same way of reduction will always result in the same configuration of lithic data.
208 This has two interconnected but unavoidable reasons: first, lithic fracture dynamics are
209 themselves ‘experimental’ (Weißmüller, 2003), only partially predictive in terms of the
210 resulting artefactual properties and with high degrees of inbuilt process and property
211 equifinality – the inherent variability of the lithic record, even under conditions of intentional
212 control, thus tends to be elevated; second, lithic artefacts – the basal units of the lithic
213 archaeological record – are the products of *plastic* and *historical* behaviour, meaning that
214 they will be imbued with added variability due to past experiences, cultural horizons, and
215 differences in technical capacity (learning, skill, etc.).

216 This brings us to the second issue: what should be replicated and how? This question
217 cannot be answered in the general, as it depends, I would argue, on what precisely we want to
218 know (showing that questions of replicability cannot be severed from larger questions of
219 knowledge aspiration and epistemology). It would be mistaken, and highly dangerous, to
220 assume that the demands of replication in fact tell us what we would like to, and as a matter
221 of fact can, know about the lithic record (means-end conflation). Data conventions also only
222 partially help us, not only because these can greatly differ across time-honed traditions of
223 lithic research (Hussain, 2019), but also since lithic studies constitutes an *observational*
224 science – in some ways more akin to ethology than computer science – and one central goal
225 of such sciences is arguably to improve and extend the very observations one can make, as
226 well as to test the productivity of *different* ways of observing. This includes the crucial
227 question of what we actually *want* to observe. Take for example contemporary *chaîne*
228 *opératoire* research in the French tradition, which aims not only to observe the variability of
229 lithic artefacts in a studied assemblage and the property space they occupy, it fundamentally
230 attempts to make observations pertaining to the dynamic formation of the assemblage as a
231 whole, i.e., how different lithic artefacts relate to each other, and thereby shape their property
232 space, due to topologically and temporally structured technological processes. The
233 observations target the *process-level*, not the object-level.

234 To replicate the findings of such lithic analysis, we therefore cannot simply mobilize
235 object-level data and analyse them in a way that makes assumptions about lithic technology
236 incommensurable with the original investigation. Instead, what may count as a replication
237 here is when another researcher sharing some broader expertise on this particular way of
238 doing lithic research would re-assess the same material and provided with the description and
239 rationalization of the observations originally made, ascertains them as trackable and
240 understandable (we do not want to replicate the discovery itself but the credibility of the

241 observations made). Importantly, it must not entail that they agree with all the details of the
242 interpretation or with the particular focus or emphasis of how these findings were
243 contextualized and presented. Curiously forgotten in current debates, replication in such cases
244 can also be experimentally achieved, by re-enacting a reconstructed knapping procedure and
245 demonstrating that the range of lithic artefacts experimentally produced closely mirrors
246 archaeological encountered configurations – a fundamental reason why refitting and
247 knapping experimentation feature as central ‘technologies of accountability’ (sensu Penders,
248 Holbrook and de Rijcke, 2019) in French *chaîne opératoire* research.

249 This example, although hardly representative of the field in its entirety, nevertheless
250 illustrates the importance of *managing our expectations* in relation to replication. It appears
251 unrealistic to set the replicability bar too narrow or high without first considering the
252 specificity of the epistemic situation, the objects of study, and the goals of lithic research.
253 Without critically examining these issues, it is impossible to know how important replication
254 really is for the field, which kind of replication matters when, and how to gauge whether
255 replication was successful, and to what extent. These issues are not only important to clarify
256 the role of replication in the field, if adequately addressed they also hold great potential to
257 improve lithic practices and the knowledge-making projects they partake in.

258

259 **A shaky crisis?**

260 Crisis talk is highly political. And this is particularly the case in archaeology where a sense of
261 deficiency vis-à-vis the so-called ‘sciences’ has time and again been invoked to further
262 epistemological and normative agendas, and to sideline others. Crisis talk is deceptive: it
263 signposts trouble, promises remedy and positive transformative change. A minimum criterion
264 for invoking crisis, however, is its empirically trackability, especially in situations where the

265 potential consequences for research practices might be severe – as in lithic research. This
266 intervention has tried to show that crisis talk in lithic studies may indeed be premature and
267 rest on a surprisingly weak empirical footing. This curiously contrasts with the sense of
268 urgency and haste conjured by a nascent body of literature positioning replication as a key
269 concern in the field. Following Pethick and colleagues (2025: 10), I argue that ‘more diligent
270 attention to the potential scope of the alleged crisis’ than hitherto offered needs to be
271 exercised, that the significance of replication in lithic studies is far from obvious, much more
272 context-dependent than often assumed, and that an archaeological metascientific research
273 programme (a science *of* lithic studies) may be needed to clarify the reality and the stakes of
274 the alleged replication crisis in the field. As is becoming increasingly clear across a range of
275 disciplines and research fields (Guttinger, 2020), extrapolating standards of replication across
276 vastly different research contexts may be highly counterproductive, and even
277 epistemologically harmful, and it may also not necessarily serve the diverse research interests
278 and aims in the field well (Vaesen and Hussain, 2025). At the bare minimum therefore, if
279 measures to enhance replication are understood as efforts to foster the credibility of science,
280 we must more openly discuss what this may mean for lithic studies and we likely cannot
281 avoid developing more evidence-based and epistemological informed approaches to the
282 problem of lithic replication.

283

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